

Microwave induced improved synthesis of monoaryl thiocarbamides, 1,3-diarylthiocarbamides, 1,3-diarylcarbamides and monoaryl-2,4-dithiobiurets

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Abstract : The 1-arylthiocarbamides (3), 1, 3-diarylthiocarbamides (6), 1,3-diarylcarbamides (7) and 1-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (11) have been synthesized by the microwave induced heating of respective reactants for about 30–60 s in solvent free condition. Reaction yields are higher with reduced time period and without the use of any solvent.

Keywords : Microwave induced synthesis of monoaryl, 1,3-diarylthiocarbamides, 1,3-diarylcarbamides, monoaryl-2,4-dithiobiurets.

Introduction

The usage of microwave energy to accelerate organic reaction is of increasing interest and offers several advantages over conventional technique^{1–4}. Synthesis of molecules which normally require a long time can be achieved rapidly in microwave oven.

In present study an attempt has been made to replace conventional method by microwave method for the synthesis of monoaryl⁵, 1,3-diarylthiocarbamides^{6,7}, 1,3-diarylcarbamides⁸ and 1-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets⁹. All these compound have been shown to have a role in the synthesis of numerous 5 and 6 membered heterocyclic systems.

Reaction scheme :

(i)

where (a) Ar = phenyl, (b) Ar = *o*-tolyl, (c) Ar = *m*-tolyl, (d) Ar = *p*-tolyl, (e) Ar = *o*-chlorophenyl, (f) Ar = *m*-chlorophenyl, (g) Ar = *p*-chlorophenyl

Scheme 1

(ii)

where (a) Ar = phenyl, (b) Ar = *o*-tolyl, (c) Ar = *m*-tolyl, (d) Ar = *p*-tolyl, (e) Ar = *o*-chlorophenyl, (f) Ar = *m*-chlorophenyl, (g) Ar = *p*-chlorophenyl, (h) Ar = 2,4,6-tribromophenyl

Scheme 2

(iii)

where (a) Ar = *p*-tolyl, (b) Ar = phenyl, (c) Ar = *o*-tolyl, (d) Ar = *m*-tolyl, (e) Ar = *o*-chlorophenyl, (f) Ar = *m*-chlorophenyl, (g) Ar = *p*-chlorophenyl

Scheme 3

(iv)

where (a) Ar = *p*-tolyl, (b) Ar = phenyl, (c) Ar = *m*-tolyl, (d) Ar = *p*-tolyl, (e) Ar = *o*-chlorophenyl, (f) Ar = *m*-chlorophenyl, (g) Ar = *p*-chlorophenyl

Scheme 4

Results and discussion

The aryl amine hydrochloride salt and ammonium thiocyanate in stoichiometric proportions were taken and

moistened with 2–3 drops ethanol in glass beaker. The beaker was irradiated for 45 s in microwave oven, when the reaction occurred and solid granular products on cooling were obtained. They were crystallized from aqueous ethanol. The melting points of these compounds were recorded. The melting point tallied with known literature values⁷ (Table 1).

The equimolecular mixture of phenyl isothiocyanate and different aryl amines on irradiation in microwave oven without any solvent for 15–30 s yielded 1,3-diaryl thiocarbamides. These were crystallized from ethanol and their melting points were tallied with known values in the literature⁸ (Table 2).

Table 1. Formation of monoaryl thiocarbamides (3)

Reactants : Aryl amine hydrochloride salt's (1) and ammonium thiocyanate (2)

Exposure time : 45 s

Sr. no.	Aryl amine salt's (1)	1-Aryl thiocarbamides (3)	Yields (%)	M.p. (°C)	Lit. m.p. (°C)
1.	Aniline hydrochlorid	1-Phenyl thiocarbamide (3a)	94	152	152
2.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine hydrochloride (1b)	1- <i>o</i> -Tolyl thiocarbamide (3b)	96	160	161
3.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine hydrochloride (1c)	1- <i>m</i> -Tolyl thiocarbamide (3c)	95	111	111
4.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine hydrochloride (1d)	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl thiocarbamide (3d)	90	189	189
5.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline hydrochloride (1e)	1- <i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl thiocarbamide (3e)	99	143	143
6.	<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline hydrochloride (1f)	1- <i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl thiocarbamide (3f)	91	141	141
7.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline hydrochloride (1g)	1- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl thiocarbamide (3g)	97	182	183

Table 2. Formation of 1,3-diaryl thiocarbamides (6)

Reactants : Phenyl isothiocyanate and aryl amines (5)

Sr. no.	Aryl amines (5)	1,3-Diaryl thiocarbamides (6)	Exposure time	Yields (%)	M.p. (°C)	Lit. m.p. (°C)
1.	Aniline (5a)	1,3-Diphenyl thiocarbamide (6a)	0	93	152	152
2.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine (5b)	1-Phenyl 3- <i>o</i> -tolyl thiocarbamide (6b)	0	94	195	195
3.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine (5c)	1-Phenyl 3- <i>m</i> -tolyl thiocarbamide (6c)	30	95	173	173
4.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine (5d)	1-Phenyl 3- <i>p</i> -tolyl thiocarbamide (6d)	0	93	140	140
5.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline (5e)	1-Phenyl 3- <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl thiocarbamide (6e)	30	98	181	181
6.	<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline (5f)	1-Phenyl 3- <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl thiocarbamide (6f)	30	96	120	-
7.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline (5g)	1-Phenyl 3- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl thiocarbamide (6g)	30	97	160	-
8.	2,4,6-Tribromoaniline (5h)	1-Phenyl 3-(2,4,6)-tribromophenyl (6h)	30	98	115	-

Note

The mixture of different aryl amines hydrochloride salt's with urea in 2 : 1 ratio on irradiation with microwave radiation for 60 s yielded 1,3-diaryl carbamides. These were crystallized from ethanol and their melting points were tallied with known values in literature⁸ (Table 3).

In similar manner the monoaryl thiocarbamides and

ammonium thiocyanate in stoichiometric proportion were taken and moistened with 2-3 drops ethanol in glass beaker. The beakers were irradiated for 60 s in microwave oven, when the reaction occurred and solid granular products on cooling were obtained. They were crystallized from ethanol. The melting points of all these compounds tallied with known literature values⁸ (Table 4).

Table 3. Formation of 1,3-diaryl carbamides (8)

Reactants : Aryl amine hydrochloride salt's (1) and urea (7)

Exposure time : 60 s

Sr. no.	Aryl amine salt's (1)	1,3-Diaryl carbamides (8)	Yields (%)	M.p. (°C)	Lit. m.p. (°C)
1.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine hydrochloride (1a)	1,3-Di- <i>p</i> -tolyl carbamide (8a)	72	265	268
2.	Aniline hydrochloride (1b)	1,3-Diphenyl carbamide (8b)	58	230	235
3.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine hydrochloride (1c)	1,3-Di- <i>o</i> -tolyl carbamide (8c)	72	255	250
4.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine hydrochloride (1d)	1,3-Di- <i>m</i> -tolyl carbamide (8d)	67	200	-
5.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline hydrochloride (1e)	1,3-Di- <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl carbamide (8e)	75	110	-
6.	<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline hydrochloride (1f)	1,3-Di- <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl carbamide (8f)	79	195	-
7.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline hydrochloride (1g)	1,3-Di- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl carbamide (8g)	80	275	-

Table 4. Formation of 1-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (9)

Reactants : 1-Aryl thiocarbamides (3) and ammonium thiocyanate (2)

Exposure time : 60 s

Sr. no.	1-Aryl thiocarbamides (3)	1-Aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (9)	Yields (%)	M.p. (°C)	Lit. m.p. (°C)
1.	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl thiocarbamide (3a)	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl 2,4-dithiobiuret (9a)	72	160	160
2.	1-Phenyl thiocarbamide (3b)	1-Phenyl 2,4-dithiobiuret (9b)	61	140	140
3.	1- <i>o</i> -Tolyl thiocarbamide (3c)	1- <i>o</i> -Tolyl 2,4-dithiobiuret (9c)	89	150	151
4.	1- <i>m</i> -Tolyl thiocarbamide (3d)	1- <i>m</i> -Tolyl 2,4-dithiobiuret (9d)	73	110	110
5.	1- <i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl thiocarbamide (3e)	1- <i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl 2,4-dithiobiuret (9e)	75	120	120
6.	1- <i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl thiocarbamide (3f)	1- <i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl 2,4-dithiobiuret (9f)	79	110	110
7.	1- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl thiocarbamide (3g)	1- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl 2,4-dithiobiuret (9g)	80	130	130

The synthesis of monoaryl thiocarbamides by conventional method require 2 h heating of reactant and pouring the contents in ice cold water⁷. But by the above described microwave induced synthesis of monoaryl thiocarbamides can be achieved in less than one minute. Also the synthesis of 1,3-diaryl thiocarbamides by conventional method require refluxing of reactant in benzene or chloroform medium for few minutes⁶. The method described above gives higher yields of products and avoids the use of toxic solvents like benzene or chloroform, which makes the present process relevantly eco-compatible.

In the same manner, the synthesis of 1,3-diaryl carbamides by conventional method require heating of reactant for 4 h in oil bath at 200 °C. The method described above gives higher yields of product and that too, within one minute. In the synthesis of 1-aryl 2,4-dithiobiurets by conventional method required 3 h heating of reactants. But by the above described microwave induced synthesis of 1-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets, these synthesis can be achieved in one minute. So, the method we are reporting in this communication is environment friendly, less time consuming, avoid use of harmful solvent and gives higher yields.

Therefore, this technique should replace earlier methods of synthesis of monoaryl, 1,3-diarylthiocarbamides, 1,3-diarylcarbamides and 1-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tube and are uncorrected. ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on Bruker Advance II 400 NMR spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard. IR spectra (KBr disc) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1800 and Shimadzu 8201 pc (4000–350 cm⁻¹) FTIR spectrophotometer.

Formation of monoaryl thiocarbamides (3) :

Reaction of aniline hydrochloride salt (1a) and ammonium thiocyanate (2) :

1.3 g of aniline hydrochloride salt (0.001 mol) was taken in 50 ml beaker. To this 0.76 g ammonium thiocyanate (0.001 mol) was added. The mixture was moistened with 2–3 drops of ethanol. It was placed in microwave oven, covered with watch glass and irradiated with microwave radiations for 45 s by keeping the wattage knob on 160 watts. After completion of reaction the beaker was removed and to it 10 ml cold water was added. The granular solid (3a) obtained was removed by filtration. It

was crystallized from boiling water, m.p. 152 °C. It showed no depression in melting point with standard sample.

IR of 3a showed absorption bands at ν_{NH} (3360 cm⁻¹), $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ (1240 cm⁻¹) and $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ (1200 cm⁻¹).

The PMR spectrum of the product (3a) showed peaks at δ 7.2 to 7.4 ppm for aromatic protons and at δ 7.95 ppm for NH protons⁹.

The other monoaryl thiocarbamides (3b-g) were synthesized by extending the reaction of aryl amine hydrochlorides salt's (1b-g) with ammonium thiocyanate (2) and related products were isolated in good yields (Table 1).

Formation of 1,3-diaryl thiocarbamides (6) :

Interaction of phenyl isothiocyanate (4) and aryl amines (5) :

Phenyl isothiocyanate 0.7 ml (0.005 mol) and aniline 0.5 ml (0.005 mol) were mixed together in Erlenmeyer flask and it was placed in microwave and irradiated for 30 s at 160 watts. After cooling the solid (6a) was isolated. It was removed with ethanol and crystallized from the same, m.p. 170 °C. It showed no depression in melting point with standard sample.

IR of the compound 6a showed ν_{NH} (3320 cm⁻¹), $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ (1320 cm⁻¹) and $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ (1280 cm⁻¹).

The PMR of the compound displayed the signals due to NH protons (δ 7.9 ppm) and aromatic protons at (δ 7.1 to 7.5 ppm)⁹.

Other 1,3-diaryl thiocarbamides (6b-h) were synthesized by extending the reaction of aryl amines (5b-h) with phenyl isothiocyanate (4) and related product were isolated in good yields (Table 2).

Formation of 1,3-diaryl carbamides (8) :

Interaction of aryl amine hydrochloride salt's (1) and urea (7) :

p-Toluidine hydrochloride salt (0.001 mol, 2.53 g) was taken in 50 ml beaker. To this urea (0.001 mol, 0.06 g) was added in 2 : 1 ratio. The mixture was moistened with 2–3 drops of ethanol and placed in microwave oven, covered with watch glass and irradiated with microwave radiation for 60 s at 160 watts. After completion of reaction beaker was removed and to it was added cold water

when the granular solid (8a) was isolated. It was filtered and was crystallized from hot ethanol, m.p. 255 °C. It showed no depression in melting point with standard sample.

The IR of compound (8a) showed absorption band for $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ (1710 cm^{-1}), ν_{NH} (3318 cm^{-1}) and $\nu_{(p\text{-disubstituted benzene})}$ (810 cm^{-1}).

The PMR of the compound displayed the signals due to NH protons (δ 8.52 ppm), aromatic proton at (δ 7.07 to 7.35 ppm) and methyl proton at (δ 2.25 ppm)⁹.

Other 1,3-diaryl carbamides (8b-g) were synthesized by extending the reaction of aryl amine hydrochloride salt (1b-g) with urea (7) and related product were isolated in good yields (Table 3).

Formation of 1-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (9) :

Reaction of 1-aryl thiocarbamides (3) and ammonium thiocyanate (2) :

1-*p*-Tolyl thiocarbamide (0.001 mol, 1.5 g) was taken in 50 ml beaker. To this ammonium thiocyanate (0.001 mol, 0.76 g) was added. The mixture was moistened with 2-3 drops of ethanol. It was placed in microwave oven, covered with watch glass and irradiated with microwave radiations for 60 s by setting the timer on 60 s position and keeping wattage knob on 160 watts. After cooling, the solid (9a) was separated. It was removed and crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 160 °C. It showed no depression in melting point with standard sample.

IR of compound (9a) showed absorption band at ν_{NH} (3310 cm^{-1}), $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ (1350 cm^{-1}) and $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ (1280 cm^{-1}).

The PMR spectrum of product (9a) showed absorption peak at δ 7.4 to 7.5 ppm for aromatic protons, at δ 2.53 ppm for $-\text{CH}_3$ and at δ 9.8 ppm for $-\text{NH}$ protons⁹.

Other 1-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (9b-g) were synthesized by extending the reaction of 1-aryl thiocarbamide (3b-g) with ammonium thiocyanate (2) and related product were isolated in good yield (Table 4).

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